

Is morphology still relevant to phylogenetic analyses?

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Phylogenetic analyses of extant taxa have relied mostly on DNA sequences. The proportion of phenomic characters relative to molecular characters has been reduced with the advent of massive parallel DNA sequencing. However, phenomic evidence enables sampling more characters and taxa without molecular data (such as fossils). Here we tested the impact of phenomic evidence on topology and support values using a total evidence approach. We quantitatively assessed five aspects of the impact of phenomics using 58 empirical data sets. First, our results demonstrated that the addition of phenomic evidence changed 90.3% (47/52) of topologies. Second, incongruences between molecular and total evidence trees are correlated with the proportion of phenomic evidence ($P < 0.05$). Third, the addition of phenomic evidence is more impactful on parsimony than maximum likelihood analyses according to Cluster Information distances ($P < 0.05$). Fourth, the addition of phenomic evidence can either reduce or increase bootstrap values. Fifth, bootstrap values from molecular clades are able to predict the occurrence of total evidence clades in most cases. However, in a few exceptions, molecular clades with 100% bootstrap values can be absent in total evidence trees. Thus, the monophyly of total evidence groups is not completely predictable based on molecular-only data. Overall, our findings strengths that phenomic evidence still matters in phylogenetic systematics.

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Repository of morphological data for deep-sea faunal novelties

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MorphoBank has become my first choice for depositing morphological data associated with scientific publications. In this brief talk, I will share my experience using MorphoBank to archive morphological datasets from five published projects (P3629, P3801, P3840, P4108, P4854) and one unpublished project under consideration. The focus will be on the repository of morphological data for deep-sea and hadal faunal novelties. I will also discuss some experiences I encountered during the submission and peer review process.

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Quantitative analysis of ophiomicrodermatoglyphics in shed-off skin: a novel taxonomic approach in snake identification

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Proper snake identification is essential for ecological research, conservation, and snakebite management, especially regarding venomous species. However, Traditional morphological methods pose envenomation risks during live handling, while molecular approaches require specialized equipment and expertise, limiting their practicality and emphasize the need for safer, more accessible alternatives. This study introduces a novel, non-invasive identification method using microdermatoglyphic features from shed-off snake skin. We examined six microdermatoglyphic characters from fifteen representative scales from the head, body and tail region of *Naja kaouthia* and *Naja naja*. Statistical analyses revealed that these features can reliably distinguish the two species and also differentiate between sexes. Among the characters, edge widest part distance (edge_wpd) was the most discriminative, significantly ($p < 0.001$) separating 93.33% of the studied scales, followed by edge_area (86.67%) and number of follicles per 20,000 μm^2 (46.67%). Microdermatoglyphic characters also significantly ($p < 0.001$) differentiated males and females in both *Naja kaouthia* and *Naja naja*, with edge_area being the most effective character distinguishing 60% of scales in *N. kaouthia* and 20% in *N. naja*, followed by number of follicles per 20,000 μm^2 (folli_20_thou), which differentiated 33% of scales in *N. kaouthia* and 13% in *N. naja*. This non-invasive approach to snake identification provides biologists a promising tool for snake taxonomy that will help better study biodiversity.

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Making academic publishing Open and FAIR: how MorphoBank aids data reproducibility

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The Open Science movement aims to make scientific research more transparent and accessible. Given the reproducibility crises and global inequity of data access, Open Science principles are more important than ever. Within an academic publishing setting, the Open Science framework makes the publication process more transparent and trustworthy, and normalises the sharing of data. We, the editorial board of the journal *Historical Biology*, are committed to Open Science and FAIR principles. *Historical Biology* is a hybrid open-access journal that publishes papers covering evolutionary and systematic biology through time, spanning both archaeology and palaeontology, and clades across the entire tree of life. We have recently undertaken a number of changes to refocus the journal, and as part of our commitment to Open and FAIR principles, we: 1) have introduced dedicated article types such as ‘Data Note’, ‘Method’, and ‘Registered Reports’; 2) are now a PCI RR-Friendly journal; and 3) have introduced dedicated editorial roles (including a Data Editor and Phylogenetics Editor). These new editorial roles strengthen our ability to support authors in making their research reproducible and replicable, both by ensuring datasets are properly managed and that manuscripts adhere to Open Science practices, including pre-registration and the use of online repositories like MorphoBank. Moving forward, MorphoBank will be our recommended repository for phylogenetic datasets, particularly from 2026 when our data sharing policy shifts to ‘Openly Available’. By promoting best practices for data management and collaboration with authors, *Historical Biology* aims to contribute to a more transparent and accessible scientific community.

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